

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF ¹⁰Be and ²⁶Al GEOCHRONOLOGY AND SURFACE EXPOSURE AGES AT THE TAERSA SITE OF THE KARAKAX FAULT

Surface	Sample name	Lat (N)	Long (E)	Elev (m)	Depth (cm)	Quartz (g)	Be carrier (mg)	Al carrier (mg)	¹⁰ Be/ ⁹ Be (10 ⁻¹⁵)	²⁶ Al/ ²⁷ Al (10 ⁻¹⁵)	¹⁰ Be (10 ⁶ atom/g)	²⁶ Al (10 ⁶ atom/g)	Lm (+ ext. uncert.)	LSdn (int. Uncert.)	LSdn (+ ext. uncert.)	LSdn (int. Uncert.)
T0SE	KXW-Pan 39*	36.33562	78.08641	3711	0	20.4503	0.3464	/	450±8	/	0.509±0.009	/	12155±945	237	12155±758	237
	KXW-Pan 35*	36.3352	78.0863	3707	0	20.050	0.3461	/	783±10	/	0.903±0.012	/	20261±1555	279	19751±1204	272
	KXW-Pan 37*	36.33505	78.0863	3706	0	20.112	0.3465	/	276±7	/	0.318±0.008	/	7908±628	201	8059±519	205
T0NE	KXW-Pan 24**	36.33717	78.08839	3729	0	26.138	0.3799	/	379±12	/	0.368±0.012	/	9138±750	299	9366±633	307
	KXW-Pan 28**	36.33619	78.08708	3720	0	25.267	0.3774	/	919±26	/	0.917±0.026	/	20414±1651	592	19881±1314	577
	KXW-Pan 42**	36.33612	78.08694	3719	0	24.964	0.3796	/	421±14	/	0.428±0.014	/	10524±871	361	10716±733	368
T0SE	KXW-Pan 32*	36.33569	78.08686	3716	0	20.130	0.3464	/	614±8	/	0.706±0.009	/	16066±1232	224	15737±959	219
	KXW-Pan 34*	36.33534	78.08664	3710	0	20.101	0.3455	/	991±14	/	1.138±0.016	/	24867±1914	355	23934±1464	342
T0SE	KR3-25 \$	36.33441	78.08694	3710	0	15.008	0.4259	/	921±17	/	1.79±0.049	/	35792±2731	941	32046±2109	892
									2.2233	2815±106	9.639±0.372	26Al: 29973±3099	1177	26Al: 29475±2826	1157	
T2SE	KXW-P5**	36.3336	78.0889	3714	0	25.657	0.3801	/	824±19	/	0.816±0.019	/	18407±1457	440	17994±1151	430
	KR3-ST2-a \$	36.33433	78.08817	3710	0	15.848	0.4395	/	841±16	/	1.56±0.044	/	29182±2359	824	27902±1839	787
								2.1199	2745±89	8.518±0.359	26Al: 26577±2780	1137	26Al: 26195±2547	1121		
	KR3-ST2-b \$	36.33433	78.08817	3710	0	15.183	0.4376	/	540±11	/	1.041±0.029	/	20158±1625	569	19655±1292	555
								7.7873	473±25	5.635±0.299	26Al: 18274±1993	979	26Al: 18406±1879	986		
	KR3-ST2-c \$	36.33433	78.08817	3710	0	15.154	0.4361	/	320±6	/	0.616±0.018	/	12618±1016	360	12583±827	359
									2.5932	716±33	2.841±0.148	26Al: 10096±1091	529	26Al: 10588±1071	555	
DP T2	KR3-3 \$	36.33433	78.08817	3710	50	15.006	0.4364	2.6239	1027±20	2614±95	1.998±0.056	10.613±0.522	/	/	/	/
	KR3-12 \$	37.33433	79.08817	3710	106	15.126	0.6625	1.1776	312±11	2565±112	0.916±0.037	4.646±0.231	/	/	/	/
	KR3-13 \$	38.33433	80.08817	3710	110	15.106	0.6573	2.4222	87±4	372±24	0.254±0.013	1.388±0.119	/	/	/	/
	KR3-18 \$	39.33433	81.08817	3710	130	15.389	0.6546	2.0230	53±2	286±31	0.15±0.007	0.874±0.103	/	/	/	/
	KR3-20 \$	40.33433	82.08817	3710	140	13.499	0.4570	0.9900	92±3	714±41	0.208±0.008	1.217±0.072	/	/	/	/
T2SW	KXW-Pan 55**	36.33561	78.08362	3705	0	25.572	0.3786	/	640±20	/	0.633±0.02	/	14634±1202	477	14405±975	470
	KXW-Pan 58**	36.33506	78.08346	3699	0	27.118	0.3784	/	726±23	/	0.677±0.021	/	15577±1279	506	15292±1034	497
	KXW-Pan 59**	36.33455	78.08461	3703	0	25.830	0.3783	/	1493±47	/	1.461±0.046	/	31770±2615	1019	30135±2039	966
T3SE	KXW-P8**	36.33362	78.09042	3717	0	6.862	0.3734	/	253±55	/	9.221±0.275	/	199175±17190	6351	188071±13245	5975
T3SE	KXW-P7**	36.33354	78.09035	3716	0	20.886	0.2935	/	9683±176	/	9.118±0.166	/	195720±16139	3812	185330±12184	3597
T3SE	KXW-P10*	36.33332	78.09059	3714	0	20.008	0.3277	/	8148±54	/	8.917±0.059	/	193279±15530	1376	183143±11565	1300
T3SW	KXW-Pan 46*	36.33608	78.08486	3724	0	20.106	0.3461	/	4079±23	/	4.692±0.026	/	101486±7897	596	97092±5945	570
T3SW	KXW-Pan 45**	36.33597	78.08498	3721	0	16.5205	0.3794	/	4126±96	/	6.331±0.1476	/	135174±11109	3298	126805±8394	3085
T3SE	KXW-P11**	36.33289	78.09108	3711	0	22.405	0.3793	/	8259±111	/	9.343±0.125	/	202703±16535	2920	190625±12299	2735
T3NE	KXW-P36**	36.33745	78.09018	3758	0	25.269	0.3797	/	10861±41	/	10.905±0.142	/	232977±19185	3293	215461±14000	3028
DP T3'	KR3-29 \$	36.33921	78.09165	3770	55	12.7368	0.3639	2.1456	4331±58	10441±361	8.279±0.199	40.878±2.006	/	/	/	/
	KR3-31 \$	37.33921	79.09165	3770	100	35.0026	0.4584	1.7434	5883±84	25547±771	5.155±0.127	29.537±0.905	/	/	/	/
	KR3-33 \$	38.33921	80.09165	3770	110	20.8226	0.3026	2.0375	3820±74	8206±235	3.715±0.103	18.688±1.001	/	/	/	/
	KR3-34 \$	39.33921	81.09165	3770	120	24.5691	0.2943	5.9325	4910±128	3497±112	3.935±0.129	19.335±0.627	/	/	/	/
T4SE	KXW-P20*	36.33283	78.09419	3740	0	20.372	0.3272	/	8540±59	/	9.165±0.063	/	195637±15738	1455	185071±11701	1371
	KXW-P17**	36.33317	78.09257	3733	0	25.926	0.3796	/	12314±165	/	12.046±0.161	/	263775±21969	3870	244714±16081	3567
	KXW-P19**	36.33271	78.09392	3736	0	25.267	0.3794	/	10783±145	/	10.82±0.145	/	234059±19299	3411	216647±14103	3139
	KR3-ST0L \$	see map	see map	3740	0	15.110	0.4376	/	6192±281	/	11.998±0.596	/	222489±21572	11912	206956±17113	11022
									2.3834	11867±519	43.572±3.376	26Al: 135936±15988	8022	Al26: 139091±14384	7702	
T4NE	KR3-ST0a \$	see map	see map	3790	0	15.001	0.4363	/	6927±132	/	13.482±0.373	/	245894±21358	7397	226885±15962	6781
								2.3458	19579±511	71.052±2.934	26Al: 223583±26172	10525	26Al: 213150±23039	9972		
	KXW-P30*	36.3356	78.09543	3786	0	20.265	0.3288	/	9412±65	/	10.206±0.07	/	213090±17244	1591	197897±12566	1470
	KXW-P21**	36.3347	78.09499	3771	0	24.5581	0.379	/	7936±108	/	8.185±0.112	/	173423±14011	2497	161960±10354	2323
	KXW-P23**	36.33473	78.09479	3771	0	24.965	0.3797	/	12080±157	/	12.276±0.159	/	263360±21912	3751	243802±15993	3449
	KXW-P26**	36.33454	78.09664	3748	0	26.150	0.3791	/	9626±127	/	9.326±0.123	/	198063±16122	2794	186999±12039	2628
	KXW-Pan 52**	36.33884	78.08673	3776	0	26.497	0.3796	/	11616±208	/	11.119±0.199	/	235556±19665	4571	217467±14428	4194
KXW-Pan 49**	36.33823	78.08601	3769	0	17.922	0.2912	/	9467±153	/	10.299±0.166	/	215554±17790	3754	200287±13112	3470	
KXW-Pan 51**	36.33906	78.08698	3778	0	18.749	0.2906	/	8528±140	/	8.856±0.145	/	185259±15142	3242	174411±1330	3041	

Samples "*" and "**" were processed at Stanford University's cosmogenic facility and samples "\$" were processed and measured at Center for Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (CAMS) at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL).

¹⁰Be/⁹Be ratios "*" were measured at CAMS at LLNL and ¹⁰Be/⁹Be ratios "**" were measured at ASTER (CEREGE).

Ages calculated with the CRONUS 3 calculator (Balco et al., 2008). Lm= Lal (1991) Stone (2000) time-dependent production rate model. LSdn = Lifton et al. (2014) model ages discussed in the text.

"See map" refer to Figure 3c, because no exact GPS location was measured in the field.

Shielding factor is 0.98; Sample density is 2.65 g/cm³ (all samples are quartzite). Thickness is ~5 cm.

Standard used at CAMS for samples "*" is 07KNSTD with ¹⁰Be isotope ratios = 2.85x10⁻¹². For samples "\$" standard is LLNL3000 with ¹⁰Be isotope ratios = 3x10⁻¹². KNSTD is the standard for Al samples.

Standard used at ASTER is NIST SRM4325 (=NIST_27900) with ¹⁰Be isotope ratios = 2.79x10⁻¹¹, equivalent to 07KNSTD.

ext. (int.) Uncert. = external (internal) uncertainty